

Contraception beyond Hormones: A Comparative Review Highlighting Barrier Methods

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Abstract

The global population is rapidly increasing, with a current growth rate of 176 people per minute, leading to concerns about overpopulation, especially in countries like Ethiopia and India. This growth has driven the search for antifertility drugs, with a focus on plant-based solutions due to their perceived safety over synthetic options. Contraception, a practice with deep historical roots, has evolved from rudimentary and often dangerous methods to modern techniques like hormonal contraceptives, IUDs, and sterilization, which offer varying degrees of effectiveness and safety. While hormonal methods alter a woman's hormonal environment to prevent pregnancy, IUDs use copper ions or hormones to block fertilization, and sterilization provides a permanent solution. Natural methods like fertility awareness and withdrawal are less reliable, with higher failure rates. Women-centric barrier methods like female condoms, diaphragms, cervical caps, and contraceptive sponges provide alternatives with varying effectiveness, typically used with spermicides for added protection. These methods offer more control but often have higher failure rates compared to hormonal or permanent options. Despite advancements, the need for effective, safe, and accessible contraceptives remains critical in managing global population growth. Including the patents obtained world wide for the barrier method of Female Contraception's since 2015-2025.

Keyword: Contraception, Hormonal and Non- Hormonal, Barrier method of Contraception, Women centric barrier method of contraception patents

Introduction

The world population is growing at an alarming rate of 176 people per minute, with a current estimate of 6 billion people predicted to exceed 10.8 billion by the year 2050. The search for antifertility drugs has continued into the twenty-first century in an effort to combat the issue of population explosion, which could have negative effects on the family in particular and society at large in general, particularly in developing nations like Ethiopia where the population growth is very high [1]. India is the world's second most populous nation and has surpassed 1.5 billion people and is growing alarmingly quickly day by day. As a result, people around the world now emphasize the regulation of fertility. Many plants and plant-based formulations have been used to safely control fertility, which has led to the creation of new antifertility molecules derived from natural products. Some active constituents were isolated and are being used in clinical studies as antifertility agents⁽¹⁾. Hence plants are convenient and preferable over synthetic contraceptives. Contraception, also known as birth control or family planning, refers to the methods and techniques used to prevent pregnancy. The history of contraception begins in the bible coitus interruptus, maiden prescription was contraceptive tampon found in Ebers Papyrus in 1550 BC. The importance of contraception spans throughout history to the present day, influencing societal, cultural, economic, and individual aspects of human life. It allows individuals and couples to control their reproductive choices by either preventing conception altogether or by timing pregnancy to align with their life goals and circumstances. Contraceptive Prevalence Rate among eligible couples was found to be 75%. Most commonly used method was tubectomy (81.6%), followed by condoms (11.4%), intrauterine devices (6.3%), and oral contraceptive pills (0.7%). Throughout history, various methods of contraception have been practiced, often rooted in cultural traditions, herbal remedies, and rudimentary techniques^(1,2). These methods were used to control family size, space out pregnancies, and manage reproductive health while some methods were effective to a certain extent, many were unreliable and carried significant health risks. Earlier to prevent pregnancy animal poop and poisonous portions, to citrus fruits and wooden blocks were used, Chinese women drank liquid lead and mercury as a contraceptive lead to adverse side effects like sterility, kidney failure, and brain damage and could also cause death.

Ancient Practices contraception has been practiced for thousands of years, with evidence of various methods dating back to ancient civilizations. In ancient Egypt, for example, the Ebers Papyrus (circa 1550 BC) references the use of contraceptive tampons made from a mixture of acacia leaves, honey, and lint. The acacia plant, when fermented, produces lactic acid, which is believed to have spermicidal properties. In ancient Greece and Rome, women used pessaries made from substances like olive oil, honey, and cedar resin to prevent pregnancy. Coitus interruptus, or withdrawal, is also one of the oldest recorded methods, mentioned in the Bible (Genesis 38:9-10).

Medieval and Renaissance Europe during the medieval period, contraception became largely associated with folk remedies and superstitions. Women used a variety of herbal concoctions and amulets to prevent pregnancy, although many of these methods were not scientifically effective. The Renaissance saw the development of more practical methods, including early forms of condoms. The first documented use of a condom made from animal intestines is credited to the Italian anatomist Gabriello Falloppio in the 16th century⁽⁴⁾

18th and 19th Centuries The 18th century marked a significant shift in contraceptive practices with the increased use of condoms, which were made from materials such as animal intestines or linen. The 19th century saw the invention of rubber condoms following the discovery of vulcanization by Charles Goodyear. This period also witnessed the development of diaphragms and cervical caps, which offered women more control over their reproductive health. Despite these advancements, contraception remained controversial and often inaccessible, with many methods being marketed clandestinely. Condoms were made up of linen, animal bladder, silk and spermicidal agents like acacia, honey, rock salt and crocodile dung were used. Sponges made up of moss, grass or bamboo were soaked in vinegar, lemon juice, cedar oil made the sperm weak, oral contraception like Queen Anne's lace seeds, lead, pomegranate seeds, silphium, unripe papaya and blue cohosh were used. (1)

20th Century Developments in 20th century was a revolutionary period for contraception. The birth control movement, led by activists like Margaret Sanger, pushed for women's rights to access contraceptive information and methods. This era saw the development of the oral contraceptive pill, first approved for contraceptive use in 1960, which became one of the most popular and effective methods of birth control. The introduction of intrauterine devices (IUDs) and hormonal implants in the latter half of the century provided additional long-term options.(5)

Modern Contraception today, a wide range of contraceptive methods are available, including hormonal methods (pills, patches, injections, and implants), barrier methods (condoms, diaphragms, sponges), and permanent methods (sterilization). Modern contraception has also expanded to include emergency contraception (morning-after pills) and non-hormonal options like copper IUDs. Advances in medical technology and a better understanding of reproductive health have made these methods safer and more effective than ever before.

Cultural and Legal Impact throughout history, contraception has not only influenced individual family planning but has also had a profound impact on society, culture, and the economy. The availability of reliable contraception has empowered women, contributed to smaller family sizes, and supported economic development by enabling women to pursue education and careers. However, access to contraception remains a contentious issue in many parts of the world, influenced by cultural, religious, and legal factors.

Contraception methods

Contraception has evolved with modern methods includes gels, foams, pessaries, capsules, suppositories, foaming tablets and melting films.

Hormonal contraception works by altering hormonal environment in women by preventing ovulation, blocking sperms by thickening cervical mucus and thinning the uterine lining to prevention of implantation. Effectiveness ranging from 1% IUD's or implants to about 7% pills with typical use

IUD's release the copper ions toxic to sperms by releasing levonogestrel to prevent fertilization. Failure rate is less than 1%

Sterilization involves the permanent methods of contraception surgical procedure to block or cut the reproductive organs in male and female, has 100% effectiveness and it is an irreversible process

Natural method involves the tracking the menstrual cycle and avowing of intercourse during fertile period or by withdrawal method before ejaculation. This method is less reliable with higher failure rate up-to 25% with typical use for fertility awareness and withdrawal method(5)

Risk associated with Contraceptives

Few methods that proposed back are controversial and even risky for example contraceptive suppositories composed of crocodile manure in combination with honey and sodium carbonate, contraceptive tampons made of lint soaked in honey and acacia tips. After insertion of tampons the gum released the lactic acid which acidifies the vaginal area, at present lactic acid is used in various contraceptive formulation like gels and creams, its noteworthy that the lactic acid is used since the ancient times (9). Vaginal part is the most acidic part in human body ranges due to production of lactic acid by epithelial cells and commensal bacteria ranges from pH 3.5 – 4. 5. (5)

Fig no. 1 Different forms of Contraception with the disadvantages

Barrier method of contraception

Barrier methods of female contraception is a physical and chemical barrier that prevent the fertilization of sperm and egg. This method is significantly used for ease of administration, reversibility and protection against the sexually transmitted infections. They avoid the body’s endocrine system and suitable for the contraception

Female condom inserted into vagina before intercourse providing the barrier to sperm and reviews says that they protect against the STIs. Typical use with failure rate is about 21% but perfect use can reduce this around 5% ⁽⁶⁾

Diaphragm is dome-shaped cup inserted into vagina to cover the cervix and block sperm entry. It is used with the spermicide for added effectiveness. Failure rate is about 17%

Cervical cap is small thimble shaped cup that fits tightly over the cervix must be used with the spermicidal agent. Failure rate is around 14 – 29 % varying with the child birth history

Contraceptive sponge is foam sponge contacting spermicide that is inserted into vagina to cover the cervix. Failure rate is about 14 – 27 % depending on delivery rate ⁽⁷⁾⁽⁸⁾

Table 1. List of Synthetic drugs showing Antifertility Activity

List of Synthetic drugs showing Antifertility Activity	
Drug	Use
Methylprednisolone	can reduce the effectiveness of birth control pills
Naproxen	decreased the concentration of prostaglandins in semen no effect on sperm density and motility
Relaxin	identified in seminal plasma delay the decline in motility and forward progression in ejaculated sperm
Salmon calcitonin	inhibit sperm motility invitro
Bromocriptine	raised prolactin levels no improvement in the sperm count results, even though prolactin levels fall
Dibromochloropropane, 1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane	impact on male fertility, causing decreased sperm counts and testicular damage
Chlorohydrins	similar to glycerol inhibits the motility of epididymal sperm effects seems to be reversible, chlorinated sugars interfere with glucose metabolism in sperm produce rapid and reversible infertility
Antimicrobial drugs: Timethoprim	reported in reduction in sperm count, but results of normal variation. Reports implicating nitrofurantoin, gentamicin and oxytetracycline remain unconfirmed
Sulphasalazine	had the semen abnormality (no endocrine abnormality)
Propranolol	when given to women it is concentrated in cervical mucus by pH trapping, 80mg oral tablet of d-propranolol
Psychotropic drugs – Diazepam, chlorpromazine or barbiturates	interfere with gonadotrophin secretion but minimal evidence chlorpromazine, imipramine and amitriptyline inhibit sperm motility in vitro at concentration higher than therapeutic blood concentration.
Amitriptyline	improve semen quality in oligozoospermia, imipramine
Alkaloids of Tripterygium wilfordii	dosage of 10 mg/kg for six weeks, it is found that the epithelial cells of seminiferous tubules in rats' testes are damaged, the number of spermatogenic cells in seminiferous tubules decreases and the wall of seminiferous tubules becomes thinner.
Medicinal plant with Spermicidal Activity	

	Name of the Plant	Common Name	Type of Plant Extract used	Experimental Model
1.	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Kadaladi	50% ethanolic extract	Rat
2.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Bael		Human
3.	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Lahsun	Crude aqueous extract	Rat
4.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem	Alcoholic extract Aqueous extract	Rat
5.	<i>Chrysophyllum albidum</i>	White star apple	Ethanolic extract	Rat
6.	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	Ber	Aqueous, methanolic and saponin extracts	Human
Medicinal plant with Antifertility Activity				
7.	<i>Abrus precatorius</i>	Chirmi	Alcoholic extract	Rat
			Ethanolic extract	Mice
8.	<i>Actinopterys dichotoma</i>	Morepankhi	50% Ethanolic extract	Rat
9.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Bael	Methanolic extract	Rat
			50% Ethanolic extract	Rat
10.	<i>Allamanda cathartica</i>	Allamanda Vine	Aqueous extract	Mice
11.	<i>Aloe Barbadensis</i>	Aloe Vera	Aqueous extract	Rat
12.	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	Sapta-pami	Methanolic extract	Rat
13.	<i>Amalakyadi churna</i>		Ethanol extract	Mice
14.	<i>Anethum graveolens</i>	Dill	Aqueous extract	Rat
15.	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Kirayat	Andrographilode	Rat
16.	<i>Barleria prionitis</i>	Vajra-danti	Alcoholic extract	Rat
17.	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Papita	Aqueous crude extract	Rat

18.	Catharanthus roseus	Sada-bahar	Alcoholic extract	Rat
19.	Curcuma longa	Haldi	Methanolic extract	Rat
20.	Fenugreek seeds		Dry powder	Rabbit
21.	Hibiscus macranthus		Aqueous extract	Rat
22.	Juniperus phoenica		Ethanolic extract	Rat
23.	Martynia annua	Bichchhu	50% ethanol extract	Rat
24.	Madhuca Indica	Mahua	Alcoholic extract	Rat
25.	Metha arvensis	Pudhina	Petroleum ether extract	Mice
26.	Piper betle	Pan	Alcoholic extract	Mice
27.	Quassia amara		Chloroform extracts	Rat
			50% Ethanolic extract	Rat
28.	Sapindus emarginatus	Ritha	Alcoholic extract	Rat
29.	Strychnos potatorum		70% methanolic extract	Rat

Table 2. Patents obtained in field of Contraception from 2015 – 2025⁽¹⁴⁻³⁰⁾

Sl. no.	Patent ID	Patent grant and duration	Title of the work	Inventors	Description
1.	CN204745334U	2015-11-11 to 2025-07-27	Memory alloy silica gel is slow-release system in utero	Xiao Yanbing, Zhang Xiaojiao, Xiao Jingsheng, Xiao Jingxin, Xiao Yuchen	The utility model discloses the memory alloy silica gel is slow-release system comprising of a skeleton adopts the winding of super elastic memory wire.
2.	CN104490512B	2017-02-22 to 2035-01-16	Condom used for treating sexual apathy and psychosexual disorder	Lin Chen Current Assignee Dai Bang Technology (Xiamen) Co.,Ltd.	The condom is made if integrated condom body with a fixed ring arranged 5 cm to 18 cm away from the body, second fixed part fixed to front end of the first ring and stimulated stick. The invention provides the

					dual stimulation for the women sexual life, improved with sexual pressure and Female with Hypoactive sexual desire disorder can also feel the sexual pressure. The sexual emotion of male is stimulated and the psychological disorder is overcome, the curative effects on treating male erectile dysfunction, male premature ejaculation are achieved.
3.	CN105559960B	2018-08-17 to 2035-12-17	A kind of intrauterine device of the degradable composite material with layered nano-structure	Lu Jiannan Current Assignee Liaoning Hao Hong Medical Science and Technology Ltd Co	Female contraceptive device, specifically degradable compound with layered nano-structure copper and iron
4.	US10406099B2	2019-09-10 to 2037-09-29	Bioerodible contraceptive implant and methods of use thereof	John H. BAILLIERuth BAILLIEGeorge BlouinNewsha FarahaniChristopher MARX Current Assignee: Gesea Biosciences Inc	A controlled release, bio-erodible pellet for subdermal implantation is offered as a method of delivering contraceptive medication. Because the pellet is bio-erodible, a contraceptive drug can be released continuously over a long period of time. Because bioerosion materials are water soluble, bio-resorbed, or both, surgical implant removal is not necessary. There are also instructions on how to use the drug delivery system, including for female contraception.
5.	JP6679759B2	2020-04-15 to 2037-04-30	Reversible hysteroscopy	Albert Chin Current Assignee	Contraceptive surgery procedure for women called fallopian tube contraceptive surgery. Inventions related to

				Boston Scientific Scimed Inc	devices, instruments and methods for reversible for implantation for surgical procedures.
6.	US10751124B2	2020-08-25 to 2038-01-05	Methods for implanting and reversing stimuli-responsive implants	Kevin Eisenfrats Gregory Grover Eric Moran Current Assignee: Contraline Inc	Reversible occlusion of body lumen, administering stimuli-responsive polymer mass in to body prevent transport. polymeric precursor material comprises natural or synthetic monomers, polymers or copolymers, biocompatible monomers, polymers or copolymers, polystyrene, neoprene, poly-etherether 10 ketone (PEEK).
7.	CN213923995U	2021-08-10 to 2030-11-06	Efficient filling and sterilizing device for female contraceptive antibacterial gel lubricant	Geng Zhongmin Qi Huiping Current Assignee Shandong Laishang Trading Co ltd	The utility model efficient filling and sterilization device female contraceptive antibacterial gel lubricant of contraception high-efficient filling degassing unit.
8.	AU2017271387B2	2021-08-19 to 2037-05-25	Enhanced intrauterine device	Martin Kuster Current Assignee: Individual	enhanced intrauterine device. Some aspects may involve a body, at least one arm, at least one connector, a communication circuit, and a removal mechanism.
9.	CN108025014B	2021-10-22 to 2036-06-23	Drospirenone-based contraceptive for overweight female patients	D. Drouin, C. Bouyer-Joubert, P. Perrin	For obese female patients, drospirenone is the only contraceptive component present in a daily active dose unit at a quantity of at least 3 mg
10.	CN215960550U	2022-03-08 to 2031-09-18	Belt type female contraceptive trousers	Xia Xintian Yan Xiaowen Xin Meichen	Belt type female contraceptives transparent panties made up of rubber. Female contraceptive trousers

				Current Assignee: Individual	
11.	CN113413490B	2022-05-27 to 2041-05-14	Ultrasonic-responsive composite hydrogel and preparation method and application thereof	Xu Wanhai, Wang Hao, Prince Qi, Qiao Zengying, Liu Zhongqing, Zhao Changhao	Covalent crosslinking ionic bond between Sodium alginate, thioketal ethylene diamine and calcium chloride for the hydrogel that can block the vas-deferens /oviduct is realized.
12.	CA2988362C	2022-07-19 to 2036-06-20	Orodispersible tablet containing estetrol	Severine Francine Isabelle JaspertJohannes Jan PlatteeuwDenny Johan Marijn Van Den Heuvel Current Assignee: Estetra SRL	Orodispersible solid pharmaceutical dosage form having weight 30 and 1,000 mg with estrol component estetrol, estetrol esters and combination of solid dosage forms for female hormone replacement therapy and female contraception for sublingual and buccal dosage form
13.	US11766400B2	2023-09-26 to 2037-10-24	Biodegradable contraceptive implants	W. Mark SaltzmanElias QuijanoFan YangZhaozhong JiangDerek Owen	Biodegradable contraceptive implants and methods of making and using thereof, are preferably formed of poly(ω -penta-decalactone-co-p-dioxanone) [poly (PDL-co-DO)], a family of polyester copolymers that degrade slowly in the presence of water.
14.	CN117562257B	2024-05-14 to 2044-01-15	High-fat low-carbon food composition and preparation method thereof	Shi Huiru, Xu Jinhong, Yang Peng, Feng Wei, Zheng Yadan Current Assignee:	A low-carbon, high-fat food composition with improved stability and health advantages is introduced by this invention. In addition to concentrated whey protein, pomegranate juice powder, and plant extracts, it contains microcapsule powders of virgin coconut oil, butter, and medium chain

					triglycerides. Active ingredients are shielded by a unique encapsulation technique, which prolongs shelf life while preserving a smooth mouthfeel and delicate coconut aroma. The mixture promotes improved yellow gas, skin whitening, intestinal relaxation, and weight loss. Long-term efficacy is ensured by auxiliary materials, which further maintain sensory attributes.
15.	US12089892B2	2024-09-17 to 2036-03-16	Systems and methods for permanent female contraception	Csaba TruckaiBenedek Orczy-TimkoJohn H. Shaddock	Tubular occlusion a minimally invasive procedure where a device is introduced into patient's uterine cavity trans cervically. One part of the procedure involves using radiofrequency energy to ablate a tiny layer of tissue in a fallopian tube segment. One can complete such a therapy in as little as one to sixty seconds. In order to induce bleeding and a subsequent adhesion formation across the coagulated blood, a second step entails cutting tissue within the ablated segment. The fallopian tube may seal permanently as a result of the segment's walls adhering and the wound healing response.

Conclusion

The alarming growth of the global population, currently estimated at over 6 billion and predicted to exceed 10.8 billion by 2050, underscores the critical need for effective contraceptive methods to manage fertility and mitigate the potential societal impacts of overpopulation. In response to this, the search for antifertility drugs and contraceptive methods has intensified, particularly in rapidly growing nations like India and Ethiopia. Throughout history, contraception has played a pivotal role in allowing individuals and couples to control their reproductive choices, with methods evolving from ancient herbal remedies and rudimentary techniques to sophisticated modern technologies.

Historically, contraceptive methods ranged from the primitive and often dangerous—such as the use of animal feces, toxic metals, and wooden blocks—to more scientifically grounded approaches like the use of pessaries, condoms, and diaphragms. The development of rubber condoms in the 19th century, spurred by Charles Goodyear's vulcanization process, marked a significant advancement in contraceptive technology, providing more reliable and safer options for birth control.

The 20th century saw a revolution in contraception, with the birth control movement advocating for women's access to reliable contraceptive methods. This era introduced the oral contraceptive pill, which became a widely used and effective method for preventing pregnancy. Innovations continued with the development of intrauterine devices (IUDs), hormonal implants, and emergency contraception, offering a broad spectrum of options tailored to different needs and preferences.

In recent years, modern contraception has further diversified, with advancements such as polymer-based implants, nanoparticle-encapsulated hormonal contraceptives, and male contraceptive gels. These innovations reflect the ongoing efforts to improve the safety, effectiveness, and accessibility of contraceptive methods. Additionally, the preference for natural products has led to the exploration of plant-based antifertility agents, offering potential alternatives to synthetic drugs.

Despite these advancements, access to contraception remains a complex issue influenced by cultural, religious, and legal factors. The availability of reliable contraception has had profound implications for society, empowering women, supporting economic development, and contributing to smaller family sizes. However, challenges persist, particularly in developing regions where population growth rates are high, and access to contraception is limited.

The evolution of contraceptive methods from ancient to modern times reflects the continuous human effort to manage fertility and control population growth. The development and refinement of contraceptive technologies have not only enhanced individual autonomy but also contributed to broader societal and economic stability. As the global population continues to grow, the importance of accessible and effective contraception remains paramount in addressing the challenges of overpopulation and ensuring a sustainable future.

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